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BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D7.5: Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1

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Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start – ending date	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WP7: Impact Maximization
WP Lead Beneficiary	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA (RAINNO)
Relevant Task(s)	T7.4 IPR Management and Sustainability Plan
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31 December 2024
Actual Submission Date	23 December 2024
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Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
09/07/2024	V0.1	ToC	Damianos Michailidis, Eleni Stogiannou, Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO)
16/07/2024	V0.3	chapter 2, chapter 3	Damianos Michailidis, Eleni Stogiannou, Anna Pouliou (RAINNO)
23/08/2024	V0.4	chapter 5	Eleni Stogiannou, Anna Pouliou, Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO)
18/11/2024	V0.5	chapter 4, summary	Damianos Michailidis, Themis Gkouthas (RAINNO)
08/11/2024	V0.7	updates on chapters 4, 5 and Annex I, II	Eleni Stogiannou, Damianos Michailidis, Ourania Ntinou, Vasilis Kotsikoris, Themis Gkouthas, (RAINNO)
22/11/2024	V0.8	External review	John Garvey (UL)
17/12/2024	V1.0	Final Version	Eleni Stogiannou, Damianos Michailidis (RAINNO)

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Recommended citation

BIOFIN-EU; Eleni Stogiannou; Anna Pouliou; Christina Dimitriou; Damianos Michailidis; Ourania Ntinou; Themis Gkouthas and Vasilis Kotsikoris; (2024) *Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1*. BIOFIN-EU EU, Deliverable 7.5, Report

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Executive Summary

The deliverable “*Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1*” (Task 7.4, WP7) focuses on developing a sustainability plan to position BIOFIN-EU in the European market, and potentially also the global, Nature-based Solutions investments market and the investments support software market. This initial plan describes the way in which the partners of the consortium are envisioning how the key results, services and tools of BIOFIN-EU are going to be sustained after the project ends.

This deliverable first provides an overview of BIOFIN-EU’s Key exploitable results (KERs). The project has identified four (4) KERs that will be available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders.

- BIOFIN Database
- BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder
- BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine
- Skills and Knowledge Accelerators

Then, it focuses on presenting the Intellectual Property Rights management methodology that is going to be used throughout the project ensuring legal protection of exploitable results. It also presents the targeted stakeholders and market segments that are relevant for BIOFIN, presenting an overview of sectoral growth, key trends, regulatory environment, and an external and internal analysis for the BIOFIN Platform. After that, the business model development methodology is presented, as well as the methodology for creating the sustainability plan for project results.

The aim of this document is to examine the main results of the project and explore different pathways ahead, present a clear and coherent market analysis, as well as exploring initial exploitation and sustainability options which will serve as a cornerstone for all discussions regarding post project exploitation between partners. The “*Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1*” provides the methodologies that will be used for exploiting different exploitation options for all project results.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	8
1.1. Project Summary.....	8
1.2. Document's Scope and Structure.....	8
2. BIOFIN-EU's Key Exploitable Results	10
2.1. Key Exploitable Results	10
2.2. Exploitation Plan	12
2.2.1. Exploitation methodology	12
3. Intellectual Property Rights Management	16
3.1. Types of IPR.....	16
3.2. Partner's obligations	17
3.2.1. Access rights	17
3.2.2. Results and ownership.....	17
3.2.3. Transfer of results.....	18
3.2.4. Access Rights to Results.....	18
3.2.5. Consequences of non-compliance.....	19
3.2.6. Non-disclosure of information.....	19
3.3. Partners' identified background	19
3.4. Methodology for defining IPRs and possible disputes.....	20
3.5. IPR Workshop: Background and Foreground Knowledge.....	22
4. BIOFIN-EU Go-to-Market-Strategy.....	24
4.1. Market Analysis.....	24
4.1.1. BIOFIN-EU Position in the market.....	24
4.1.2. Market size estimation for BIOFIN-EU.....	28
4.1.3. Regulatory environment in the EU	29
4.1.4. Market Drivers	30
4.1.5. SWOT Analysis	31
4.2. Business Model development.....	32
4.2.1. Business Model Development Methodology	32
4.2.2. Business Model Tools	35
5. Sustainability plan	42
5.1.1. Marketing Strategy for ensuring sustainability	43
5.1.1.1. BIOFIN-EU Mission and Key Messaging.....	43
5.1.1.2. Customer Personas.....	44

5.2. Next steps on Sustainability Plan	49
6. Conclusion.....	50
7. References	51
Annex I	54
Annex II	55

List of Figures

Figure 1: “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool.....	13
Figure 2: Steps for the identification and inclusion of a new KER.....	13
Figure 3: Inclusion of newly identified IPRs.....	20
Figure 4: Example of IPR’s notification procedure	21
Figure 5: “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool - IPR protection type example.....	22
Figure 6: 1st IPR workshop on 12/06/2024.....	23
Figure 7:Percentage of Direct and Supply Chain Gross Value Added (GVA) with High, Medium and Low Nature Dependency, According to Industry.....	25
Figure 8: Climate finance relative to finance for NbS.....	26
Figure 9: Carbon Credit Market Expansion	27
Figure 10: TAM, SAM, SOM	28
Figure 11: Sustainable Collaborative Business Model Development Process by Ploutos H2020	33
Figure 12: Business Model Canvas Template	36
Figure 13: Lean Startup Canvas	38
Figure 14: Value Proposition Canvas.....	39
Figure 15: Service Dominant Business Model Radar (SDBM/R) template	40
Figure 16: Modified Business Model Canvas for non-commercial result.....	42
Figure 17: Benefits of persona use suggested in literature.....	45

List of Tables

Table 1: Key Exploitable Results Matrix (Marketability: C: Commercial, N: Non-commercial).....	10
Table 2: BFMULO Matrix	14
Table 3: Characterisation table for potential exploitable results.....	15
Table 4: Identified specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation and exploitation of results..	20
Table 6: PESTLE analysis template for the external environment.....	30
Table 7: SWOT analysis template	32
Table 8: BIOFIN-EU’s Vision, Mission and Value Proposition	44

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
BM	Business Model
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
GTM Strategy	Go-to-Market Strategy
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MVP	Minimal Viable Product
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental
R&D	Research and Development
SAM	Serviceable Available Market
SOM	Serviceable Obtainable Market
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TAM	Total Addressable Market

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

If biodiversity is to be placed back on a path to recovery, new tools and knowledge are required to redirect financial resources from destructive economic activity towards nature-positive investment. The financial system consists of interacting and dynamic actors who value certainty (rules and governance structures) and efficiency (outcome transparency and low monitoring costs). BIOFIN-EU aims to create a unifying framework and technology that creates the enabling conditions for nature-positive investments. Activities that protect and restore biodiversity (such as nature-based solutions) are frequently unique, multi-actor efforts carried out on a local scale with positive, but complex outcomes. Project partners' resolve this by establishing a categorisation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) alongside a menu of good governance structures and a library of stakeholder engagement. This will draw on expertise and best practice in natural capital and economics to streamline decision making and accelerate transaction completion by standardising the investment process and creating the enabling conditions for large-scale finance. To accelerate nature-positive business models, we create a data analytics and underwriting engine to advance conventional project appraisal and risk assessment and account for and model expected outcomes. BIOFIN-EU will assess and validate its approach across diverse real-life case studies (learning sites). These findings and approach will initiate a twin green and digital transition that resolves transaction complexity and creates the enabling conditions for large-scale investment that are required if the EU is to achieve its biodiversity goals. Project outcomes will identify remaining gaps in Taxonomy and support policy forming through evidence-based recommendations and we will co-design, develop and establish pathways for skills and knowledge accelerators for the European financial services industry

1.2. Document's Scope and Structure

The present Deliverable 7.5 - Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1 is developed within the framework of Task 7.4 "IPR Management and Sustainability Plan"; WP7- Impact Maximization. The aim of the deliverable is i) to develop a sound IPR management scheme in order to identify all relevant IP and clarify ownership, screening and managing any new IP that arises during the lifespan of the project; ii) to present available business model state-of-play and deliver tailor-made Business Models (BMs) for project results incorporating the trends in the market and iii) to create a Sustainability Plan indicating the actions to be performed after the end of the project in order to achieve future uptake of the solutions in the whole EU data and food supply chain. Delivered in M12, D7.5 will be updated at M24 and M36, presenting progress with updates and improvements following the incorporation of feedback from project partners and related stakeholders towards the finalisation of the business model and BIOFIN-EU's sustainability plan.

More specifically for each version:

- **D7.5:** This first version includes all the methodologies that will be used during the project with regards to IPR Management, Go-to-Market Strategy, Business Models Development and Sustainability Plan Development for both commercial and non-commercial results. It also includes a preliminary Market Analysis of all relevant markets for BIOFIN-EU's results, an analysis of the regulatory environment regarding NbS investments in the EU and customer personas created to better understand BIOFIN-EU's target audience, help with results development and give insights into future communication and marketing efforts.

- **D7.6:** This version will report on IPR activities that happened until M24. It will also include an updated version for Go-to-Market Strategy (final market analysis, and analysis for external & internal environment) and Business Model for BIOFIN-EU result exploitation.
- **D7.7:** The final version of this deliverable will report on IPR activities that happened until M36. It will also include updates for all preliminary analyses, if necessary, the final version of BIOFIN-EU's Business Model, and the Sustainability Plan for both commercial (financial projections, marketing strategy) and non-commercial results (other types of exploitation except commercial, potential partnerships, and results maintenance after the end of the project).

The document is outlined in 7 chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall logic behind the creation of BIOFIN-EU's IPR plan, business model and sustainability plan for an efficient and effective integration and implementation of the project. The chapters that this document is comprised of include:

- Chapter 1: provides a summary of the project, the document scope, and its overall structure.
- Chapter 2: identifies BIOFIN-EU's Key Exploitable Results, KPIs and exploitation plan
- Chapter 3: indicates the IPR management plan
- Chapter 4: provides a thorough Go-to-Market Strategy plan including market analysis, regulatory environment, market drivers, SWOT analysis and analysis of the framework for business models development
- Chapter 5: outlines the sustainability plan that will ensure BIOFIN-EU's future
- Chapter 6: Conclusion
- Chapter 7: References

2. BIOFIN-EU's Key Exploitable Results

This first version of the **Integrated toolset for multiplying impact** sets the ground for the successful exploitation and protection of the project's results in terms of commercial use/reuse of the services and tools developed/created within BIOFIN-EU, by defining an initial framework of rules and recommendations.

2.1. Key Exploitable Results

BIOFIN-EU has identified four (4) Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that will be available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders.

- BIOFIN Database
- BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder
- BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine
- Skills and Knowledge Accelerators

Regarding their exploitation, all results incorporate both non-commercial (N) and commercial (C) exploitation aspects, meaning that they can be used as technological foundations, scientific knowledge and prototypes and thus, promote further R&D in the area of financing and biodiversity, develop new marketable services and processes, and/or utilize them as new standardization and policy recommendations.

BIOFIN-EU listed these KERs along with their Unique Value Proposition (UVP). Each UVP is a concise statement - addressing both technical and non-technical audiences, showing how each of the KERs solves a specific stakeholder problem and adds a particular value. This list can be updated and validated through iterative sprints together with the relevant project partners.

Table 1: Key Exploitable Results Matrix (Marketability: C: Commercial, N: Non-commercial)

Exploitation Goal		By whom	For whom
KER 1 N&C	BIOFIN Database: A data platform incorporating high quality Biodiversity and ES data from heterogenous and multiscale NbS sources. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial		
	<u>Academia:</u> Exploitation of the NBS/ES data for conducting new breakthrough research. <u>Financial Actors and Professionals:</u> Effective data platform facilitating internal, R&D activity and evaluation of 'external' third party NBS solutions	UL, NAT, QUB, IST, SERDA, UNIPD, ETI, ILSI	Research Organisations, Financial Actors
UVP	The Database will be enriched with both NBS-promotor and NBS-provider led trustworthy and accurate data.		
KER 2 N&C	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder: Innovative Business Models that will support the decision-making towards NBS lending/investments. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial.		
	Strengthen the position of NBS - Promoters/Providers based on principles of mutuality, facilitating the collaboration with various value chain actors and creating win-win situations. Unlock new business opportunities and enter new markets for service providers in real time.	IOB, ILSI	Financial Actors, NBS Providers

UVP	Tailor-made business models designed to match the specific needs (e.g. Risk Assessments, reduced transaction costs) of all stakeholders, developed as a system with a sectoral approach and validated in real life use cases through the 8 unique BIOFIN learning sites.		
KER 3 N&C	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine: A user-friendly dashboard that allows discovery, purchase / use and contribution of ES/NBS raw data and analytics services running on the BIOFIN NBS Dashboard. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial		
	<p><u>Data owners</u> will use friendly services of the marketplace to publish information available on their own platforms (i.e, data providers) and monetize them.</p> <p><u>Data consumers</u> (e.g. Corporations, Financial Institutions, Public enterprises, Policy makers & regulators) will be able to explore available tools and information empowering their decision support processes.</p>	IOB, ILSI	<p>Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies</p>
UVP	Effective and all-encompassing decision-making support tool, enhancing competitiveness and efficiency.		
KER 4 N&C	Skills and Knowledge Accelerators: The portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies, mentoring courses of the BIOFIN activities will be publicly available through open repositories and under a Creative Commons licence during the lifespan of the project. Free during the lifespan of the project and then commercial.		
	<p>Transfer of new knowledge and capacity, upscale the skills development for current professional bankers and investment managers as well as the next generation of business leaders.</p>	IOB, SUL, ILSI	<p>Professional Ecosystem</p>
UVP	Comprehensive training courses, business simulations and associated tools and models, providing a curriculum emerged through testing in real life settings.		

A complete exploitation strategy has already been established in M03 as part of the DEC plan, designed to bring BIOFIN-EUs results to all target groups and deliver sustainable outputs that extend beyond the project lifetime. The strategy will follow a multi-actor approach through 4 cycles:

Cycle 1: Investigate - Explore partner expectations and ambitions for future business development. BIOFIN-EU will base its initial strategy for management of Intellectual Property (section 2.2), by performing an IPR Scan for all partners. IP expectations information collection form and individual interview, resulting in an agreed-upon set of IPR measures.

Cycle 2: Co-create - Continuous mapping of current trends, market watch and analysis. BIOFIN-EU will proceed towards the validation of exploitation scenarios (commercial & non-commercial) and identify the best market fit following the pace of progress of each pillar to capture accumulated value fully.

Cycle 3: Accelerate - Finalise agreements on results' exploitation through dedicated workshops. Define (non)commercial synergies with potential partners/collaborators.

Cycle 4: Financial Planning - Determine financial benefits and projections for all the consortium partners capitalising the BIOFIN-EU outcomes. Optimization in terms of cost (and time if necessary) of their provided services or products will be showcased for at least three years after the end of the project while financial forecasts will be conducted for the identified KERs and the possibilities of their commercial exploitation. Release the final version of the Integrated Toolset.

The post-project sustainability plan (T7.4) will be developed, also aiming at the sustainability of BIOFIN-EU's results.

2.2. Exploitation Plan

The BIOFIN-EU exploitation plan will effectively:

- Ensure the **use, re-use** and extensive dissemination of knowledge created during the project
- Highlight the **added value** of the project to promote further scientific development
- Promote **sustainable growth** (e.g., industry competitiveness)

Exploitation may take multiple forms:

- **Financial exploitation:** building sellable products and/or monetized services
- **Research and development:** involving new projects with experience drawn from the project
- **Education:** courses, training, and workshops
- **Community building:** raising awareness around the project's topics, problems, and solutions
- **Knowledge transfer:** through publications and collaborations among or between target groups
- **Policy contribution:** encouraging broad adoption of solutions or frameworks for regulation, standardisation, or funding support for solution uptake

2.2.1. Exploitation methodology

A specific procedure has been set for the definition of the project's KERs, the identification of new KERs other than those already identified, their validation, characterization and development of the final exploitation plan of each KER from a specific partner, group of partners or external organisation.

The **first step** involves the development of the "KERs Inventory & IPRs" online tool, which validates the existing knowledge and information about the project's Key Exploitable Results and possible IPRs that the partners have already identified.

In this tool, the list of the identified KERs is provided where partners are asked to state the scope of exploitation, the KERs' target groups, the means of exploitation and to identify possible IPRs that derive from the exploitation of the identified project's results. For each partner there is a separate sheet with their organisation's acronym providing them an individual space for information and updates (Figure 1).

The tool has been already shared with the partners and is available for further update at any time:

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-3) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>		<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)</i>	<i>Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant</i>
		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>		
1	BIOFIN Database	Commercial		Research Organisations, Financial Actors	<i>"This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation."</i>
2	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder	Commercial		Financial Actors, NBS Providers	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>
3	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine	Commercial		Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>
4	Skills and Knowledge Accelerators	Commercial		Professional Ecosystem	<i>If relevant, please indicate the means of exploitation</i>

Figure 1: "KERs Inventory & IPRs" online tool

This tool includes:

1. KERs
2. Scope of exploitation
3. Target groups [to whom]
4. Means of exploitation
5. Linked IPRs to KERs

The **second step** involves the identification of possible additional exploitable results that may be developed during the project. Towards this direction, constant communication with partners, updates for their progress on the 3 use cases either through the regular partners' meetings or through direct communication with the involved partners, help in identifying possible exploitable results, commercial or non-commercial.

To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Steps for the identification and inclusion of a new KER

When one or more partners identify a new KER, the partner has to inform the WP7 Leader (RAINNO) and the coordinator (UL) providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by

making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. The partner has to provide all relevant information about this KER using the “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool uploaded on the project’s SharePoint (**Annex I**), covering at least the following aspects:

- Description of the exploitable result
- Scope of exploitation (scientific, commercial, policy making, training, other)
- Target groups
- Means of exploitation
- IPR(s) linked to the KER, if relevant.

Once the form has been completed, it will be shared with the coordinator as the starting point for discussion. Each new KER will be presented at the General Assembly for the consortium to validate. This is particularly important to ensure that the partners who will exploit the result and the target groups are properly identified, particularly if joint exploitation is a factor. If there are no objections, the KER will be included in the list and a distinct strategy for its exploitation will be developed.

The **third step** refers to the assessment of the exploitation strategy for each KER. To efficiently determine the involvement of project partners in each of the KERs the BFMULO Matrix will be implemented, in which the partners will state (in M24 or M36) their exploitable intentions using the following list:

B = IPR’s on background information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.

F = IPR’s on foreground information, Information including all kinds of exploitable results generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project. To have an F in an exploitable result it is necessary that a partner has a task(s) in the project related to that very result.

M = Making the products, manufacturing, and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.

U = Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilisation of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.

L = Licensing the result, therefore earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the Consortium.

O = Other, any other exploitation means (e.g.: consultancy, provide services, etc.).

Table 2: BFMULO Matrix

#	Short name	KER1	KER2	KER3	KER4
1	UL				
2	NATURALIS				
3	UGOT				
4	UM				
5	RAINNO				
6	SERDA				

7	UNIPD				
8	ETIFOR SRL				
9	IOB				
10	SULITEST				
11	ILSI				
12	QUB				
13	COFAC				

In later stages, a characterisation table will be provided to partners which will exploit the project’s key results. Each result requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type, whether it can be commercialised, which relevant **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** protections are required (if any) and who will exploit the result. The characterisation table will be offered to partners to characterise exploitable results (Table 3). This table aims also to collect information for the Sustainability Plan and the Go-to Market Strategy that will be developed by the end of the project. The information and feedback included in the characterization table will serve as the foundation of the final exploitation plan of the KERs.

Table 3: Characterisation table for potential exploitable results

CHARACTERISATION OF EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	
<p>MARKET</p>	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?
	What is the anticipated time to market?
	What is the size of the market in M€ and relevant trends?
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of licences?
	Who are the competitors?
	How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?
<p>STEPS TOWARDS EXPLOITATION</p>	When is the expected date of achievement?
	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?
	What are the costs incurred after the project and before exploitation?
	Which partners will be involved in results development?
<p>IPR STATUS</p>	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?

3. Intellectual Property Rights Management

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are the ownership rights for creations of the mind, such as inventions, names, images, or designs and can enable owners to obtain financial benefit from their ideas. Striking the right balance between creator and public interests can foster creativity and innovation. BIOFIN-EU will examine the protection of any results that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited, and if possible, reasonable, and justified, protect them.

3.1. Types of IPR

The most common forms of IPR protection include:

- **Patent:** an exclusive right granted for an invention. It allows the owner to decide how and whether the invention can be used by others.
- **Trademark:** a sign that distinguishes goods and services of one enterprise from those of another.
- **Industrial design:** includes the aesthetic aspect of an object. 2D features can include patterns, lines, and colours, whereas 3D features extend to shape and surface.
- **Copyright:** is the legal term to describe the rights over literary and artistic work but can also extend to databases, advertisement, maps, and technical drawings.
- **Trade-secret:** commercially valuable confidential information which may be sold or licensed. This can include technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, lists of customers.
- **Confidentiality:** information that is not publicly known and warrants protection.
- **Geographical indication:** indicate the specific geographical location of origin or a product and its characteristics that are uniquely attributed to that area.

The choice of the most suitable form will be based upon the specifications of the activity and its results.

BIOFIN-EU will produce significant research results and technological innovations. Hence, a strategy that will handle all IP rights matters will be developed, creating an encouraging environment for further exploitation of the discoveries and knowledge generated. As such, BIOFIN-EU handles IPR Management in a three-level approach:

During the project: BIOFIN-EU will give emphasis to the protection of IPRs derived from the project implementation, ensuring that any IPR generated shall rest with the industry that created it and can further exploit it commercially. Under this framework, a set of both protective and supportive measures (such as the obligation to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements) will be undertaken by the consortium to create confidence in all participants. Knowledge Management and democratisation of scientific knowledge: The consortium will publish the overall project results through publications, seminars and in the project website, without charging intellectual property rights. Further, partners will deposit scientific peer reviewed publications in a centralised repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the HE “Open science policy”. More information regarding backgrounds identification, the specific frameworks that will be used during the project and the first IPR workshop that has already been implemented can be found on sections 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 later in the chapter.

Post-Project IPR Strategy: Systematic management of IP risks is the building block of post-project sustainability. To this end, RAIN will offer services for the whole IPR lifecycle to BIOFIN-EU partners concerning appropriate protection of results, provided that protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (T7.4).

3.2. Partner's obligations

BIOFIN-EU will follow all IPR management requirements described in the Grand Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

3.2.1. Access rights

'Background' means any **data, know-how or information** — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and
- needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to the rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Grant Agreement.

According to the Consortium Agreement and specifically Article 9, the Parties have identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and have also, where relevant, informed each other that Access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

3.2.2. Results and ownership

'Results' means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.2 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities including but not limited to research contracts in national and European funded projects with third parties provided it does not lead to any commercial or monetary benefit to third parties involved in such cooperative research project on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s);
- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licences to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

Granting authority

The **granting authority** has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notably summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any

other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes — during the action or afterwards.

The right to use the beneficiaries' materials, documents and information is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive, and irrevocable licence, which includes the following rights:

- A. use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to people working for the granting authority or any other EU service (including institutions, bodies, offices, agencies, etc.) or Member State institution or body; copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers; and communication through press information services)
- B. distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display, or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes)
- C. editing or redrafting (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (e.g., meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g., audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation)
- D. translation
- E. storage in paper, electronic or other form
- F. archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- G. the right to authorise third parties to act on their behalf or sub-license to third parties the modes of use set out in Points (B), (C), (D) and (F), if needed for the information, communication and publicity activity of the granting authority

If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including intellectual property rights or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned).

3.2.3. Transfer of results

According to the Consortium Agreement, **ownership of a party's own results may be transferred**, including its share of jointly owned Results, following the procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement.

In the case of ownership transfer to the third party, the third party must be identified in Attachment (3) of the Consortium Agreement and the other Parties must waive their rights to prior notice and to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement.

The transferring Party must inform the other Parties at the time of transfer and will **ensure the rights of other Parties are not affected** by such a transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after signing the Consortium Agreement requires a decision from the General Assembly.

3.2.4. Access Rights to Results

Access Rights to Results if needed for exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement.

A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

For the avoidance of doubt any grant of Access Rights not covered by the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement shall be at the absolute discretion of the owning Party and subject to such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the owning and receiving Parties

3.2.5. Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary **breaches any of the obligations** of the Grant Agreement (Section 2), the **grant may be reduced**.

3.2.6. Non-disclosure of information

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to any other Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is "Confidential Information".

The Recipients hereby undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on nondisclosure under the Grant Agreement, for a period of 5 years after the end of the Project:

- A. not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- B. not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
- C. to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- D. to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive, or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care regarding the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

3.3. Partners' identified background

According to the GA, "background" is defined as "data, know-how or information (...) that is (...) needed to implement the Action or exploit the results". In other words, background IP is anything that pre-existed by the owner before the time of an agreement between parties. Because of this need, Access Rights have to be granted in principle, but Parties must identify and agree amongst them on the Background for the Project. BIOFIN-EU's Consortium Partners Identified Background, which is relevant to the IPR, can be found in table 4 below:

Table 4: Identified specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation and exploitation of results

Participant Number	Short Name	Country	Identified Background relevant to IPR	Restrictions

3.4. Methodology for defining IPRs and possible disputes

After having identified and validated the project’s exploitable results and the market in which these results will be introduced, the commercial results have to be linked to possible intellectual property rights to ensure their proper use and distribution to the market. The methodology for defining these IPRs is aligned completely with this for defining the project’s exploitable results. To this end, the procedure and steps are the following:

Figure 3: Inclusion of newly identified IPRs

For the identification of possible IPRs, the KERs online form presented in Figure 5 includes a section for this purpose.

Figure 4: Example of IPR's notification procedure

According to the procedure (Figure 4):

- Partners that have identified possible IPRs that derive from the exploitation of one or more commercial results, need to inform the Coordinator and the WP6 leader (RAIN) on the IPR(s) that is/are linked to the respective KER(s)
- Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR(s). Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, the IPRs are validated accompanying the respective KER(s).
- An IP dispute arises when an IP notification is received and one or more partners do not agree with an aspect of the notification: it may be due to ownership, IP description or dependencies.
- Conflicting partners have **15 days** to reach an agreement.
- The coordinator will call the conflicting parties after **15 days to track the agreement**.
- Is there an IP agreement?
 - **Yes:** agreed IP notification to RAINNO
 - **No:** IP conflict is escalated by the coordinator to GA to take a decision.

When the project's results are more concrete, thus the IPRs clearer, partners will fill the table in the online tool that has been provided to them for the results that they will exploit. For these KERs there is a section in the characterisation table asking partners to provide information on the way they intend to protect the identified results, i.e., with copyright, a trademark etc.

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-4) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>		<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)</i>
		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>	
1	BIOFIN Database	Commercial	<input type="text" value=""/>	Research Organisations, Financial Actors
2	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder	Commercial	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Scientific Commercial Policy-making Training and education Other </div>	Financial Actors, NBS Providers
3	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine	Commercial	<input type="text" value=""/>	Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies

Figure 5: “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool - IPR protection type example

3.5. IPR Workshop: Background and Foreground Knowledge

BIOFIN-EU has already designed and will deliver a sound IPR management scheme coupled with **2 IPR-dedicated workshops** in order to identify all relevant IPs and clarify ownership, screening and managing any new IP that arises.

One workshop has already been delivered by RAINNO on 12/06/2024 (Figure 6) during the Plenary Meeting of the BIOFIN-EU project in Limerick, Ireland, with the purpose of clearly explaining the IPR management framework and procedures to partners. The event agenda was as follows:

1. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (IP) & INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR)
2. IP IN EU FUNDED PROJECTS / IP MANAGEMENT
3. IP MANAGEMENT IN BIOFIN-EU
4. WORKFLOW
5. Q&A

After the end of the workshop the materials used, presentation and template, were shared amongst the partners. The IPR presentation was also uploaded to SlideShare and the official project’s [SharePoint drive](#).

Figure 6: 1st IPR workshop on 12/06/2024

The other workshop is going to happen around the middle/end of the project. It will mainly be concerned with Foreground IP, with each partner examining the possibility of protecting its results generated during the project, if:

- protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified
- the results can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited

The ownership of the results can be

- Single Ownership: Who generated it – owns it, or
- Joint Ownership: If the partners have jointly generated the results and it is not possible to establish their respective contribution, the partners automatically become joint owners.

4. BIOFIN-EU Go-to-Market-Strategy

BIOFIN-EU's Go-to-Market-Strategy (GTM) strategy and sustainability planning development follows a lean multi-actor approach - a combination of the lean start-up methodology that focuses on the development of Minimal Viable Products (MVP) in short iterations and the multi-actor approach that stresses the active involvement of various stakeholders. RAIN will simultaneously monitor the project (tech & non-tech) outcomes that are beneficial for the BIOFIN-EU consortium to design a strategy for the successful market uptake of innovative solutions. BIOFIN-EU's exploitation strategy is designed to bring project results to all target groups and will be updated and enhanced over the BIOFIN-EU lifespan, aiming to deliver sustainable outputs that extend beyond the project duration. To this end, BIOFIN-EU will recognise amongst others the NbS market as well as the competitive landscape; BIOFIN-EU's ambition is to synchronise and align its project findings and tools with dominant financial institutions. GTM strategy will provide a plausible path to commercialise BIOFIN-EU innovations.

4.1. Market Analysis

The Market Analysis chapter serves as a critical lens through which the intricacies and dynamics of the current landscape are examined. In this chapter, a comprehensive analysis is going to be presented that includes market size estimations, growth drivers and bottlenecks for all the different markets that BIOFIN-EU and its stakeholders operate accompanied with a TAM, SAM, SOM analysis. Those markets include: (i) the overall *market for nature-based solutions*, where the BIOFIN-EU platform could potentially be used as a way for banks to assess NbS before providing a loan; and (ii) the *market for online investment platforms*, where the BIOFIN-EU platform could potentially be used as a way for investors to rank NbS investment opportunities and help them decide where to allocate their capital. Key statistics are going to be provided, including market size estimations, growth trends, and restraints. Furthermore, the competitive landscape is identified, and finally, an external and internal analysis is going to be conducted in the form of PESTLE and SWOT analysis respectively.

4.1.1. BIOFIN-EU Position in the market

In the EU, the market for investments in nature-based solutions is still in an early stage. An analysis of existing databases and online resources was conducted by the European Investment Bank (2023) to gain insight into the current landscape and diversity of nature-based solutions across the European Union. This analysis brought together information on 1,364 projects with in-field implementation within the EU and the United Kingdom, representing the largest known collection of data on such initiatives in the region. Despite this, there are notable data gaps—a challenge acknowledged in the broader literature on global nature-based solutions—meaning conclusions drawn are primarily qualitative, particularly regarding the types and scale of projects in progress. In certain areas, the potential for nature-based solutions aligns with opportunities for ecosystem restoration.

Some key findings of the analysis include:

- Public funding is the predominant financial source for nature-based solutions, corroborating existing literature. Only 3% of identified projects report private sector funding exceeding 50% of their total costs.
- Nature-based projects are generally limited in size: 72% span less than 1 km², and 81% report investment costs below €10 million (with 44% under €1 million).

- The current implementation pace for nature-based solutions remains slow. Across most ecosystems examined, the projected scale of use over the next decade is significantly lower than the estimated potential based on ecosystem conditions.
- Agricultural landscapes stand out in terms of funding availability. Ample financing through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is theoretically sufficient to support additional nature-based solutions and associated benefits across the EU. However, questions persist regarding the efficiency and effectiveness of these funds when applied to nature-based projects.

Additionally, the United Nations (UN) and the World Economic Forum (WEF) estimate that investment in nature-based solutions must at least triple in real terms by 2030 and grow fourfold by 2050 to achieve global targets for climate change, biodiversity, and land degradation. This increase would translate to a cumulative investment of up to \$8.1 trillion and a required future annual investment of \$536 billion (WEF, 2021).

Biodiversity and ecosystem services are essential foundations for economies in tangible and measurable ways. Industries highly or moderately dependent on nature and its services generate an estimated US\$44 trillion in global value added, over half of the world’s GDP, with US\$13 trillion attributed to high-dependency industries and US\$31 trillion to moderate-dependency sectors (WEF, 2020). Those sectors are depicted in Figure 7. Key sectors, including construction, agriculture, and food and beverage industries, rely heavily on direct resource extraction from forests and oceans, as well as on

Figure 7: Percentage of Direct and Supply Chain Gross Value Added (GVA) with High, Medium and Low Nature Dependency, According to Industry

the regulatory and supportive services ecosystems provide. These dependencies bring inherent risks. For these sectors, biodiversity loss is a material concern, impacting both performance and financial stability. For instance, **the decline of pollinators would have immediate repercussions on 75 percent of food crops that rely on animal pollination, affecting annual crop outputs valued between US\$235 billion and US\$577 billion.** Similarly, the degradation of vital marine ecosystems, such as mangroves, seagrass beds, and coral reefs, would likely impact global fisheries, which are critical to numerous value chains. As biodiversity loss

progresses, the resulting physical risks influence the productivity of economic activities, specific sectors, and various geographic areas (World Bank, 2021).

UNEP (2021) reports that around **US\$133 billion per year is currently invested in nature-based solutions (NbS)**, using 2020 as the baseline. **Public funding constitutes 86%** of this total, while **private financing accounts for 14%**, equivalent to **US\$18 billion annually** (Figure 7). This contrasts sharply with investments in climate solutions, where the private sector is the primary funding source.

Figure 8: Climate finance relative to finance for NbS

Future investments in NbS will require active participation from both the public and private sectors, with carbon credits expected to play a pivotal role (Figure 8). To meet global targets for climate change, biodiversity, and land degradation, NbS investment must at least triple by 2030 and increase fourfold by 2050 as already mentioned in 4.1.1. However, financial flows detrimental to biodiversity, such as fossil fuel and agricultural subsidies, continue to overshadow biodiversity-focused finance. Each year, government support that potentially harms biodiversity is estimated to be five to six times greater than total spending on biodiversity (OECD, 2020), with the volume of "brown finance"¹, funding that conflicts with biodiversity objectives, likely being significantly larger.

¹ "non-sustainable financing and investments which support the fossil fuel industry or carbon intensive activities" (definition taken from [GEMET](#))

Figure 9: Carbon Credit Market Expansion
 (Source: https://www.iif.com/Portals/1/Files/TSVCM_Report.pdf)

The field of NbS finance is still in its early stages. Investors are already achieving substantial returns at scale within the food and agriculture sectors, although other areas will require more time to fully develop. What may once have seemed ambitious is likely to become a mainstream investment opportunity sooner than expected, paving the way for a transformative era.

Except for the NbS investments market the other relevant market that BIOFIN-EU is going to be active on is the **Online Investment Platform Market**. This market was valued at **US\$1.88 billion in 2021** and is **projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.9% from 2022 to 2030**. The rising popularity of cryptocurrency as an asset class and its adoption as an investment vehicle are expected to fuel market expansion over the forecast period. Additionally, the increasing number of online investors worldwide is likely to drive industry growth. The integration of P2P payment options within online investment platforms, offering enhanced security and safer transactions, further supports the positive market outlook (Grand View Research, 2022).

The increasing number of High-Net-Worth Individuals (HNWIs) globally, along with their heightened interest in digital investments, is expected to drive market growth over the forecast period. HNWIs are particularly valued by private equity firms due to the added requirements to manage and protect their investments. The rise of blockchain technology is also a key factor in market growth. Blockchain offers advantages for addressing disputes and resolving data inconsistencies, thus gaining prominence in online investment platforms. Additionally, the expansion of blockchain-enabled trading platforms, such as CoinSwitch Kuber, supports market growth by enabling users to invest and trade in cryptocurrencies. The market is further driven by the efficiency of these platforms, with fast order execution and low latency, which save time and reduce costs for investors and traders. Government initiatives worldwide to promote digitalisation are also expected to fuel growth over the forecast period, alongside the rising demand for personalised online investment platforms. Nevertheless, concerns regarding the security of online investment platforms could limit growth, as could technical challenges like optimisation issues. Conversely, increased awareness of online

investment platforms in developing economies presents new growth opportunities, as does the **rising demand for cloud-based investment solutions** (Grand View Research, 2022).

In this current environment the BIOFIN-EU platform that is being developed aims to act as a bridge between the people implementing nature-based solutions and people wanting to invest in them. The overall goal is to help redirect capital from traditional investments to nature positive ones, increase private participation in the sector, help in speeding up implementation of nature-based solutions and in scaling them up. Consortium partners assess the platform will be in a unique position to capture this new expanding market since it is being developed by experienced industry professionals that know the key needs and wants of investors.

4.1.2. Market size estimation for BIOFIN-EU

In the realm of market analysis, defining the market's dimensions and growth trajectory is crucial, particularly when considering the market's existing advancements and its sustainability over time. For BIOFIN-EU, these aspects can be explored through the **TAM, SAM, and SOM framework**, a methodology that dissects the market into specific subsets. This approach is instrumental in providing a clear snapshot of the market's potential.

TAM (Total Addressable Market) signifies the entire revenue opportunity that exists within the market for a specific product or service. **SAM (Serviceable Available Market)** narrows down this scope to the segment of the market that can be reached or served. Finally, **SOM (Serviceable Obtainable Market)** is the portion of SAM that the business can capture, considering its business model, resources, and limitations.

For BIOFIN-EU, applying the TAM, SAM, and SOM framework is a strategic move to comprehend the vast landscape of the agriculture technology market. It enables the project to:

1. Identify the Total Addressable Market (TAM): Understand the full potential of the market for advanced agricultural technologies and AI-driven solutions, setting the upper limit for market expansion.
2. Determine the Serviceable Available Market (SAM): Focus on the specific segments of the market that Smart Droplets can effectively target and serve, considering the project's unique value proposition and technological capabilities.
3. Estimate the Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM): Realistically assess the portion of the market that Smart Droplets can expect to capture, factoring in competitive positioning, market penetration strategies, and operational capacities.

Figure 10: TAM, SAM, SOM

By dissecting the market through the TAM, SAM, and SOM lens, BIOFIN-EU aims to strategically position itself within the continuously evolving and expanding market of NbS investments and investment platforms. This methodical approach provides a robust foundation for strategic planning, resource allocation, and market entry decisions, ultimately propelling BIOFIN-EU towards accessing and capitalizing on this dynamic market sector. This analysis will take place during the second year of the project's runtime, when more precise information will be available regarding specific platform functionalities, thus allowing for a better and more accurate assessment of the serviceable market size.

4.1.3. Regulatory environment in the EU

The regulatory landscape within the EU for NbS investments is evolving to align with the EU's broader environmental, climate, and sustainability goals. The EU's regulatory framework recognises the critical role of NbS in meeting the Union's targets for biodiversity, climate adaptation and mitigation, and sustainable development. However, the framework presents both opportunities and challenges for investors in NbS projects, with a complex network of policies, directives, and funding mechanisms influencing investment dynamics.

EU Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy

The **European Green Deal** (EC, 2019), introduced in 2019, sets the agenda for the EU's transition to a sustainable economy and aims to position the Union as the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Integral to the Green Deal, the **EU Biodiversity Strategy** (EC, 2020) for 2030 highlights NbS as essential to achieving biodiversity and climate resilience objectives. This strategy calls for the restoration of at least 20% of the EU's degraded ecosystems by 2030, including urban, forest, and agricultural landscapes, and places NbS at the core of the EU's approach to climate resilience and ecosystem health. The Biodiversity Strategy, the EU has introduced regulations such as the **Nature Restoration Law** (EC, 2020), which mandates member states to set and monitor specific ecological restoration targets across various ecosystems. These regulations create a framework within which public and private entities can engage in NbS investments, promoting environmental resilience through economic incentives and regulatory requirements. This approach is complemented by initiatives like the European Climate Law, which enshrines the 2050 climate neutrality target and provides a stable policy framework that indirectly supports NbS investments as tools for carbon sequestration and ecosystem-based adaptation.

Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities

The **EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities** (EC, 2023) is a classification system that provides investors with guidance on economic activities considered environmentally sustainable. The Taxonomy includes specific criteria for "*nature-based solutions and ecosystem services*", offering a clear framework for investors to assess NbS projects' compliance with sustainability objectives. The Taxonomy is expected to channel private finance into projects that contribute to biodiversity conservation and ecosystem resilience. However, as NbS is a broad and multi-sectoral field, implementing the Taxonomy in this context remains challenging, with ongoing efforts to further define and standardise NbS metrics for improved transparency and accountability.

EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

The **EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** (EC, 2021) encourages farmers to adopt sustainable practices, including NbS, through agri-environmental schemes and incentives. CAP reforms increasingly integrate biodiversity and climate requirements, thus expanding the potential for NbS adoption in rural landscapes. Similarly, the EU's 'Fit for 55' package, a set of policy proposals to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by

at least 55% by 2030, supports NbS by incentivising carbon sequestration through reforestation, wetland restoration, and soil carbon enhancement.

Funding Support

Several EU funding mechanisms encourage NbS investments, aiming to reduce the financial risk and support project implementation. The EU’s **Horizon Europe programme** (EC, 2020), with a €95.5 billion budget for research and innovation (2021-2027), includes funding lines specifically targeting NbS research and demonstration projects. Moreover, the **LIFE programme**, the EU’s primary financial instrument for environmental and climate action, has allocated a significant portion of its funding to support NbS, particularly in the areas of climate adaptation and ecosystem restoration. The **InvestEU programme** (EC, 2024) also provides funding guarantees to facilitate public-private partnerships in NbS, enhancing investor confidence in emerging NbS markets.

Overall, the EU’s regulatory framework is progressing rapidly, with ambitious targets and supportive policies that incentivise public and private investments in NbS projects. The EU will likely keep introducing continuous adaptation and refinement of regulatory frameworks, in order to encourage NbS investments, contributing to its climate, biodiversity, and sustainability goals.

4.1.4. Market Drivers

Advancing from the identification of target users in BIOFIN, the subsequent phase in market analysis involves a meticulous examination of market drivers. For this purpose, BIOFIN-EU will employ PESTLE Analysis, an analytical framework that considers Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors. These factors collectively shape market trends, needs, and barriers, serving as crucial drivers that influence the market landscape.

Understanding market trends and needs is vital; while they can pose challenges when entering a new market, they also present opportunities to gain a competitive edge. Recognizing the dynamic and evolving nature of the market, it is equally important to acknowledge the potential barriers that might impede the introduction of new technologies.

Table 5: PESTLE analysis template for the external environment

Political	Economic	Social
Technological	Legal	Environmental

BIOFIN-EU, aspiring to effectively introduce its innovative solutions into the market, will conduct a comprehensive **PESTLE** Analysis. This analysis will provide deeper insights into the macro-environmental factors potentially impacting the project’s market success. The key market drivers, as identified through the PESTEL framework, include:

- **Political:** This category considers the influence of government policies, regulations, and political stability on a business. It involves factors such as taxation, trade tariffs, labour laws, government stability, and political ideologies.
- **Economic:** Economic factors analyse the economic conditions, trends, and indicators that can affect a business. This includes factors like inflation rates, exchange rates, economic growth, and consumer spending patterns.
- **Sociocultural:** This category delves into societal and cultural factors that might influence a business. It includes demographics, cultural norms, social values, lifestyle changes, and consumer behaviour.
- **Technological:** Technological factors assess the impact of advancements in technology on a business. This involves factors like innovation, automation, research and development, and the pace of technological change.
- **Legal:** Legal factors involve the examination of laws and regulations that affect a business. This can include investment and environmental laws, equal opportunities etc.
- **Environmental:** Environmental factors consider the impact of ecological and environmental consequences of a business. This category includes factors related to sustainability, climate change, environmental regulations, and the company's environmental responsibility.

By considering these external factors in the PESTLE analysis, a more comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and threats that the platform faces can be achieved. Following the assessment of external factors through PESTLE analysis, an assessment of internal capabilities for BIOFIN-EU through SWOT analysis is going to be presented in the next chapter.

4.1.5. SWOT Analysis

Conducting the PESTLE analysis prior to the SWOT analysis enables a more comprehensive understanding of BIOFIN-EU positioning within its environment. The insights gleaned from the PESTLE analysis serve as inputs for identifying opportunities and threats in the SWOT analysis, thereby enhancing the comprehension of internal strengths and weaknesses (Perera, 2017). Following these analyses, the findings can contribute to formulating an initial strategy plan or business model.

A SWOT analysis melds together both external and internal assessments to succinctly outline your Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. To illustrate, consider a new business with the following observations:

- **Strength:** Enthusiastic employees or a unique product, knowledge expertise in a specific area.
- **Weakness:** Lack of an existing customer base, limited financial resources.
- **Opportunity:** Prospective customers in need of the product's solution, along with keen investors, market demand for the product is increasing.
- **Threat:** Competition from well-established businesses with larger budgets, highly volatile raw materials prices.

The goal is to identify opportunities that align with the strengths of an organisation and devise strategies to address threats to the organisation while mitigating significant weaknesses, while mainly having in mind the exploitation of all BIOFIN-EU KERs as one platform (at least that is the current most probable scenario), the main project result that encompasses all others. For example, SWOT analysis may help in pinpointing the most promising customer segments to target. Consequently, an organisation might opt to explore online

avenues for customer outreach and begin exploring methods to secure additional investments to shore up financial vulnerabilities.

Table 6: SWOT analysis template

ANALYSIS OBJECTIVES	
Based on everything discussed so far, identify the main strengths and opportunities that are going to help in establishing BIOFIN-EU as a credible platform for NbS, supporting financiers in their decision-making process, penetrate the market and overcome operational challenges and external threats.	
INTERNAL FACTORS	
STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
EXTERNAL FACTORS	
OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –
NEXT STEPS	
Develop a Business Model for BIOFIN-EU platform exploitation.	

4.2. Business Model development

This chapter serves as an indispensable guide within this report, offering a comprehensive overview and strategic insights into diverse business models development frameworks. This will help in developing BMs for the Key Exploitable Results of the project later on.

4.2.1. Business Model Development Methodology

In today's dynamic landscape creating and adapting one's business model is pivotal for sustainable success. The chapter not only dissects various proven business model methodologies but also provides key considerations to empower BIOFIN-EU partners in navigating the complexities of the external environment. The sustainable collaborative business model method developed by project [Ploutos H2020](#) can be used for developing businesses and products. It is utilised as a resource or framework that facilitates the creation, analysis, and communication of business models in a collaborative and interactive manner. Furthermore, it is a process particularly valuable for startups, entrepreneurs, and businesses looking to innovate and adapt their business strategies.

The process of the sustainable collaborative business model is highly interactive as the resulting business models prioritise the creation of shared value through collaboration. The process is divided into 5 phases: Analysis, Design, Evaluation, Implementation and Scaling.

Figure 11: Sustainable Collaborative Business Model Development Process by Ploutos H2020

1) Analysis

The analysis phase consists of three essential steps: individual alignment, exploration and ambition, and understanding. During the analysis phase, the first two steps are combined where it is crucial to evaluate the stakeholder's strategic intentions, their perception of the innovation, and identify potential risks they may encounter. This valuable feedback information is currently being gathered through bilateral and general meetings with BIOFIN-EU project partners, discussing individual results, their potential capabilities, and how they can work as a whole. Once insights have gathered, BIOFIN-EU will align the stakeholders' objectives and establish trust and commitment among them.

2) Design

The design phase is an iterative process. This phase comprises three steps: development, evaluation, and adaptation. In the development step, the insights gained from the analysis phase will be used as a starting point. This is a necessary step to further concretize BIOFIN-EU's value proposition, define the roles of each actor, and establish the distribution of costs and benefits. These aspects will be thoroughly discussed and agreed upon by all stakeholders, and the outcome will be a preliminary draft of the sustainable collaborative business model.

3) Evaluation

The evaluation phase consists of an assessing step, and here a more formal evaluation of the business model took place. Four criteria will be discussed/analysed in this phase:

- Viability which assesses whether the benefits are higher than the costs for each stakeholder. In all cases, stakeholder benefits are assessed to be higher than the costs, since all groups have significant benefits from improved connectivity infrastructure.
- Feasibility to evaluate how feasible the implementation of the business model is. Suggested BMs for the KERs are evaluated as feasible, since there is already an expanding market for NbS investment (that KER exploitation falls into).

- Robustness to assess whether the business model can adjust to future changes. This is assessed qualitatively through partner's feedback and quantitatively using scenario analysis in conjunction with the financial projections (see chapter 5).
- Desirability to evaluate whether the business model is strategically important and wanted. This again is assessed internally but also externally with stakeholders.

In the evaluation step the proposed business models, thoroughly assessed by partners, will have the opportunity to suggest any necessary alterations while in the third step, all the points of evaluation are taken into account. This happened during bilateral meetings with project partners in conjunction with meetings for BM creation. BIOFIN-EU partners should reflect individually and jointly on these four criteria to conclude the evaluation phase. A formal decision will be made to either continue with the development of the business model or not based on the results of the assessment. This process will take place in the following months, will be finalised before the end of T7.4 and will be presented in D7.7. BIOFIN-EU will continuously structure the decision-making process by revisiting the objectives defined taking into account the challenges identified throughout the process.

4) Implementation

The implementation phase will include the roadmap step. BIOFIN-EU's goal is to create a clear and detailed roadmap for the successful implementation of the business model. A business roadmap is a visual timeline that highlights strategic goals and initiatives. It reflects the organization's prioritized efforts. The roadmap will ensure that all stakeholders are aligned in their activities, which is crucial given the interdependent nature of the model. Through a collective effort, all stakeholders will contribute to the design of the roadmap towards an effective implementation of BIOFIN-EU's Business Model. The proposed framework to follow for creating the roadmap is described below.

A business roadmap typically includes the following information organized in vertical or horizontal axes:

- **Goals:** These are the targets the organization aims to achieve, such as revenue or growth. These could include goal statements for the organisation or project but also specific measurable goals like number of sales, cost reduction percentage etc.
- **Initiatives:** Major themes of work or areas of investment that align with organisational goals. Those could include a campaign, a new product/feature launch, staffing, operations etc.
- **Milestones:** Significant points of progress. These can include having an integrated version of your online platform, secure funding, first sale/contract.
- **Dependencies:** Anything that must be completed before other tasks can start or that might impact progress, such as interrelated work items or external stakeholders.

Since it is still very early and KERs development has not been finalised, this exercise is purposeful to happen towards the end of the project and again be presented in D7.7 due in M36.

5) Scaling

The scaling step will involve the monitoring step. During this stage, BIOFIN's stakeholders will keep track of the performance of the sustainable collaborative business model by monitoring its progress. Opportunities for scaling up can be identified and pursued by revisiting all previous phases of the process to assess their resources and capabilities, evaluate the business case for scaling and re-evaluate the business model using the same criteria of viability, feasibility, robustness and desirability. This step is purposeful to happen after the end of the project, when KERs will have been finalized, fine-tuned and their actual exploitation can start.

Collaboration and alignment are key to this iterative process and the outcome should be a formalised design for a sustainable collaborative business model which can be applied to BIOFIN-EU's results.

4.2.2. Business Model Tools

“Business model tools are commonly used to describe and communicate business model ideas” (Athanasopoulou and De Reuver, 2020) and are conceptualised, in research, as boundary objects that are meant to make possible the exchange of information between, often disparate in nature, stakeholders (Bouwman et al., 2017). For this report, an apt definition of Business Model Tools can be found in (Bouwman et al. 2020), where business model tools are described as *“the use of methods, frameworks or templates (here referred to as tools) to facilitate communication and collaboration regarding business model analysis, (re-)design, adoption, implementation and exploitation”*.

Business models are usually generated by strategic management tools that can visualise and assess concrete business ideas or concepts. A business model tool represents different fundamental elements of a business and aims to clarify how different aspects of the business are related to each other. The goal of a business model tool is to provide a quick overview of the business model without many details (compared to the traditional business plan). The visual nature of the business model tool should make it easier to refer to and understand by anyone.

Below, there are brief descriptions of commonly employed business model tools that enjoy widespread usage:

- Business Model Canvas
- Lean Startup Canvas
- Value Proposition Canvas
- Business Model Radar
- Prototype Canvas

Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas is a business model tool, i.e., it is a visual chart with elements describing a company's or product's value proposition, customers, infrastructure including its partnerships, and financial aspects. It has been widely adopted in practice for designing business models (Osterwalder and Pigneur 2010). However, it follows an organisation-centric approach that renders the model from the perspective of a single company, as opposed to a network-centric view (Turber et al. 2015). It focuses on the processes controlled by the focal company and pays less attention to the customers' active role in value co-creation.

A particular characteristic of the Business Model Canvas is that Osterwalder and Pigneur, who invented the Business Model Canvas, insisted that the Business Model Canvas should always be a one-page document. The main reason for this is that, the Business Model Canvas being a business model tool should bear a single, robust message: how to implement the strategy of the business model. Another reason is that Osterwalder advised the use of graphical icons in business modelling as much as possible (Prabhu et al. 2013) in order for the message to be pithy and succinct:

Figure 12: Business Model Canvas Template

The Business Model Canvas, understandably, incorporates the nine building blocks: value proposition, partner networks, customer segment, customer relationship, channel, key resources, activities, revenue streams, and cost structure (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). A brief explanation of each block is presented below:

1. **Key activities:** The most important activities in executing a company's value proposition.
2. **Key resources:** The resources that are necessary to create value for the customer. They are considered assets to a company (or, in the case of the project, the Consortium) that are needed to sustain and support the business. These resources could be human, financial, physical and intellectual.
3. **Key networks:** In order to optimise operations and reduce risks of a business model, organisations usually cultivate buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. In the case of the project such networks are expected to emerge from the networks of each participating partner, but also from networking activities undertaken by the implementation effort itself.
4. **Value propositions:** Services a business (or, in the case of the project, an economic actor in general) offers to meet the needs of its customers. The value proposition provides value through various elements such as newness, performance, customization, "getting the job done", design, brand/status, price, cost reduction, risk reduction, accessibility, and convenience/usability. The Project's use case results should be at the core of the value proposition.
5. **Customer segments:** To build an effective business model, any economic actor offering a service must identify which customers it tries to serve. The project's use cases will provide a point of direction for this particular building block, but it is also the main task of the business model to determine potential customer segments for its use cases.

6. **Channels:** The Project can deliver its value proposition to its targeted customers through different channels. Effective channels will distribute the value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient and cost effective. In the case of the BIOFIN-EU, the value proposition can reach potential clients through channels developed during the project's lifetime (store front), partner channels (major distributors), or a combination of both.
7. **Customer relationships:** To ensure the survival and success of any business endeavour, responsible project partners will have to specify the type of relationship they want to create with their identified customer segments. In the case of the project, that element should address two critical steps of a customer's relationship: How the new business will get customers and how the business will keep customers purchasing or using its services.
8. **Cost structure:** This describes the most important monetary consequences while operating under different business models. The cost structure can be cost-driven and value-driven. Given that costs are absorbed in the case of the Project through its funding, the cost structure is expected to be value driven.
9. **Revenue streams:** The way the potential business opportunity is expected to generate income from each customer segment. This building block is expected to be further elaborated upon further in the analysis. In conclusion, the Business Model Canvas is a business model tool which has met with wide acceptance from the business community and beyond. Its plasticity has rendered it immensely popular amongst other business model tools and its robustness has solidified its reputation as a valid tool for business model implementation.

Lean Startup Canvas

The Lean Startup Canvas, or Lean Canvas as it is most usually encountered, is an adaptation of Osterwalder and Pigneur's Business Model Canvas which self-identified entrepreneur Ash Maurya proposed in his 2012 book *Running Lean: Iterate from Plan A to a Plan That Works* (Maurya, 2012). The Lean Canvas promises an actionable and entrepreneur-focused business plan, as it focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages (Abdoun and Ibrahim, 2018). As is the case with the Business Model Canvas the Lean Startup Canvas is a business model tool, i.e., its purpose is meant to convey a robust message in a succinct way.

It shares multiple common characteristics with the Business Model Canvas, but it also draws heavily from lean management methodology, the purpose of which is to identify and do away with all non-value-added activities which are a potential source of improvement in any kind of business process. The lean perspective is to reduce waste and costs, to improve quality and gain better use of resources in order to deliver higher value to customers (Cabrita et al., 2016). Maurya's intent was to come up with a Business Model Canvas which would be more actionable and more easily understood than the original Business Model Canvas, but it should also be more applicable to start-ups.

As was the case with the Business Model Canvas the Lean Startup Canvas is also meant to be kept at a single page-length; the concept is, as before, that the message should be apt, concise and succinct. It aspires, however, to prove even more plastic than its counterpart, in the sense that its purpose is to be used by anyone, implying that the Business Model Canvas is largely reserved for those who share an understanding of economic and business terminology (Figure 12):

LEAN CANVAS

Title: _____ Created By: _____ Date: _____

PROBLEM List your top 1-5 problems.	SOLUTION Outline a possible solution for each problem.	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Single, clear, compelling message that states why you are different and worth paying attention.	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE Something that cannot easily be bought or copied.	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS List your target end users.
EXISTING ALTERNATIVES List how these problems are solved today.	KEY METRICS List the key numbers that tell you how your business is doing.	HIGH LEVEL CONCEPT List your X for Y analogy (e.g. YouTube = Flickr for videos).	CHANNELS List your path to customer (inbound or outbound).	EARLY ADOPTERS List the characteristics of your ideal customers.
COST STRUCTURE List your fixed and variable costs.		REVENUE STREAMS List your sources of revenue.		

Figure 13: Lean Startup Canvas

Since the Lean Startup Canvas draws so much from the Business Model Canvas and has such a similar appearance, it is deemed more useful to briefly number the differences between the two business model Tools, rather than enumerate, as was previously done, it's - also - nine building blocks.

1. Intuitive: Lean Startup Canvas uses layman terms in order to become more appealing to every stakeholder and not only those with a specific skill-set or know-how.
2. Customer-Problem-Solution Focused: Lean Canvas prioritises customer-problem-solution. This exemplifies why the business model tool is particularly geared to facilitate start-ups.
3. Simpler: Lean Startup is meant to be used as a stand-alone business model tool, not requiring a complimentary Value Proposition Canvas [see following chapter], as is the case sometimes with the Business Model Canvas.
4. Practical/actionable: The rationale behind the development of the Lean Canvas is that it is entrepreneur focused, making it more practical than a business plan and more actionable than the Business Model Canvas.

Whether the Lean Canvas delivers on its promise as a more actionable and simpler alternative to the Business Model Canvas is a question, however the particular focus of the specific business model tool on startups is something that creates advantages but also poses limitations in its applications.

Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) is a strategic tool (Kandee, 2020) that helps organisations and businesses to understand and design the value they provide to their customers. It was created by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur as part of their Business Model Canvas framework (Osterwalder et al., 2014). Clark et al., 2012 stated that at the centre of the Business Model Canvas there is the Value Proposition, which represents the value offered to customers and can be seen in Figure 14.

The Value Proposition Canvas is more than just a graphical representation of customer wants. It focuses specifically on the value a product or service offers to its target customers and how it addresses their needs and pain points (How to Use Value Proposition Canvas: The Definitive Guide, 2020). The Value Proposition Canvas can be used when there is a need to improve an existing product or a service offering or when creating a completely new offering.

The Value Proposition Canvas provides on the one hand the analysis of the customer side which helps you to define your target customer segments, which are the specific groups of people or organisations you are trying to serve. You can identify their characteristics, behaviours, preferences, and needs. Understanding your customer segments is crucial for tailoring your value proposition effectively. On the other hand, the value proposition contains ways to solve customer problems, relieve concerns and meet expectations. When two canvases align, it indicates that the product and/or service contains the desired values by customers and thus, it helps the organisation design products and services that their customers want (Osterwalder et al., 2014)

As mentioned above, the Value Proposition Canvas is formed around two building blocks (Lindic & Da Silva, 2011): by capitalising the experience in the area of the Customer Segment, i.e. Customer Jobs, Gains and Pains you are able to create Value Proposition for Products and Services, Gain Creators and Pain Relievers (Pokorna et al., 2015). Organisations need to create one profile for each customer segment.

Figure 14: Value Proposition Canvas
(Source: [Strategyzer.com](https://www.strategyzer.com), 2024)

Business Model Radar

Changes in market dynamics, customer preferences, technological advancements, and competitive pressures are some of the reasons that drive organisations to transition into a service-dominant (SD) business setting. This shift is driven by the recognition that value is co-created through interactions between organisations and customers. By focusing on services, organisations can better align with customer needs, adapt to changing market dynamics, and create sustainable competitive advantages in today's rapidly evolving business landscape (Turetken and Grefen, 2017).

The conceptual tool that can be used as a guiding reference for business model design is the Service-Dominant Business Model Radar (SDBM/R) (Turetken et al., 2018). A service-dominant business model differentiates from the traditional business model by taking a network structure based on the service-dominant (SD) logic rather than the value chain approach of the goods-dominant (GD) logic (Lüftenegger, 2014). SDBM/R has a network-centric design at its core, allowing the composition of service design in multi-party business networks. It defines how the actors in the business ecosystem participate in value co-creation and what the cost–benefits distribution is (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Service Dominant Business Model Radar (SDBM/R) template
(Source: Grefen et al., 2016)

In a SDBM/R the following main elements can be distinguished (Turetken et al., 2018, Lüftenegger, 2014, Lüftenegger & Softic, 2019) as shown in the picture above:

- The co- created value-in-use is the goal of the business model and constitutes the heart of SDBM/R.
- The actor value proposition represents the part of the central value-in-use contributed by a single actor.

- The next layer, co-production activity defines the activities that each actor performs in the business in order to achieve the co-creation of value, in other words its actor value proposition.
- The third frame actor cost/benefit represents the costs and benefits that an actor incurs and gains respectively, by performing co-production activities.
- The fourth and last frame represents the actors, and they can be distinguished between Customer (contributes to the production of the value- in-use), Focal Organization (often initiates the setup of the business model and participates actively in the solution), Core partner (contributes to the essentials of the solution), and Enriching partner (enhances solution's added value-in-use).

Designing service-dominant business models using the SDBM/R technique involves an engaging and iterative procedure that requires the direct involvement of the main stakeholders within the business model. Even though SDBM/R models are known for their user-friendly nature, they serve as a robust foundation for translating business models into conceptual business process models. These process models depict the real-world business operations within collaborative networks, facilitating the effective implementation of the intended business strategies (Suratno et al., 2018).

Selection of the tool

By taking into account the literature review presented above regarding the various business model tools and also the specific characteristics of the KERs that are still early in development, one of the aforementioned tools is going to be selected. During the second iteration of this deliverable (M24), a rationale will be presented here that explains this choice. After that, a preliminary version of the BM will be showcased that is later going to be refined and presented in its final form in the final iteration of the deliverable (M36).

5. Sustainability plan

In this part of the deliverable, the first draft of the sustainability plan both for commercial and non-commercial results will be presented.

For BIOFIN-EU results that will be deemed to be commercially viable by the end of the project, this plan will provide the roadmap for **achieving long-term goals and will document strategies to continue the program, activities, and partnerships** by answering key questions such as:

- Future Income streams and mitigation strategies concerning them;
- Financial Projections;
- Marketing strategy for ensuring BIOFIN-EU’s sustainability;
- Ways to attract new customers and businesses;
- Possible future diversification to fit with changing NbS investments environment and the future needs of end-users;

For non-Commercial Results the sustainability plan for the long-term exploitation of non-commercial results to ensure their use/reuse continues after the project is no longer funded by Horizon EU and will consider:

- Alternative exploitation options;
- Responsible partners;
- Resources required (including person hours, technology);
- The value of results and what needs to remain exploitable;
- Specific tasks/ activities required for the result to remain valuable;
- Partnerships or joint actions that could better support long term exploitation than only the partners themselves;
- Alternative funding sources;

NON-COMMERCIAL RESULT – MODIFIED BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Figure 16: Modified Business Model Canvas for non-commercial result

A sustainability plan aims to create a balanced, responsible, and resilient organisation by addressing environmental, social, and economic considerations. It seeks to integrate sustainability into the core of the business, foster stakeholder engagement, and drive continuous improvement in sustainable practices.

5.1.1. Marketing Strategy for ensuring sustainability

5.1.1.1. BIOFIN-EU Mission and Key Messaging

In developing a Marketing plan one of the first things that has to be done is **creating a mission for the organisation**, able to clearly communicate it. BIOFIN-EU's mission statement is as follows:

"BIOFIN-EU aims to establish a comprehensive framework and technology that fosters the necessary conditions for nature-positive investments."

As also stated in BIOFIN-EU's website the main objectives of BIOFIN-EU are:

1. Create and test solutions to quickly and effectively gather and share valuable biodiversity and Ecosystem Services data.
2. Understand preferences and regulations of capital owners, financial institutions, and NbS-providers to integrate governance aspects into business models, financial instruments, and associated technologies.
3. Develop trustworthy, accurate, and fair data sharing of biodiversity and Ecosystem Services outcomes to reduce transaction costs and other barriers to nature finance.
4. Design and test new business models and biodiversity-linked investments that maintain protections for NbS-providers and their communities while securing long-horizon benefits for NbS-promoters.
5. Integrate relevant processes, systems and reporting and disclosure requirements and support organisations in directing financial flows towards biodiversity protection and restoration.
6. Build knowledge and skills among current and future finance professionals and decision-makers and build a community to advance the implementation of the regulations to co-develop solutions and accelerate the financial flow of funds towards biodiversity-linked activity.
7. Examine i) opportunities arising from specifically, nature positive investment by analysis preferences among shareholders, bond investors, consumers and retirees; ii) transition costs associated with the re-allocation of finance from destructive economic activity; iii) financial models associated with corporate performance as well as fund management performance.

Having well-defined messages to convey is an essential element for any business. This practice facilitates the establishment of connections with customers, fosters brand recognition and loyalty, and ultimately generates sales. Consequently, it becomes imperative for all businesses to grasp the art of utilising marketing communications effectively in order to fulfill their objectives. By implementing appropriate strategies and techniques, businesses can extend their reach to a broader audience, thereby enhancing the potential for customer acquisition and revenue growth.

A last thing to keep in mind is that value proposition for all the Key Exploitable Results have been created and are presented below:

- **NbS Database:** A data platform incorporating high quality Biodiversity and ES data from heterogenous and multiscale NbS sources.
- **Nature-Positive Business Model Builder:** Innovative Business Models that will support the decision-making towards NbS lending/investments.

- **Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine:** A user-friendly dashboard that allows discovery, purchase / use and contribution of ES/NbS raw data and analytics services running on the BIOFIN-EU NbS Dashboard.
- **Skills and Knowledge Accelerators:** The portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies, mentoring courses of the BIOFIN-EU activities will be publicly available through open repositories and under a Creative Commons licence during the lifespan of the project.

Table 7: BIOFIN-EU’s Vision, Mission and Value Proposition

VISION	MISSION	VALUE PROPOSITION
<p>Unlock finance to protect and restore biodiversity</p>	<p>BIOFIN-EU aims to establish a comprehensive framework and technology that fosters the necessary conditions for nature-positive investments.</p> <p>BIOFIN-EU is actively innovating and experimenting with novel approaches for capturing, aggregating, and analysing biodiversity and ecosystem services (ES) data. The goal is to minimise transactions and reporting costs associated with finance that supports the protection and restoration of biodiversity.</p>	<p>NbS Database: A data platform incorporating high quality Biodiversity and ES data from heterogenous and multiscale NBS sources.</p> <p>Nature-Positive Business Model Builder: Innovative Business Models that will support the decision-making towards NbS lending/investments.</p> <p>Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine: A user-friendly dashboard that allows discovery, purchase / use and contribution of ES/NbS raw data and analytics services running on the BIOFIN-EU NbS Dashboard.</p> <p>Skills and Knowledge Accelerators: The portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies, mentoring courses of the BIOFIN-EU activities will be publicly available through open repositories and under a Creative Commons licence during the lifespan of the project.</p>

Having established clear goals and objectives for the organisation, the next part would be to examine specifically the marketing Key Performance Indicators that can help the BIOFIN-EU platform to penetrate the market and also to define a marketing mix that outlines the key decisions that can be made by managers in the future to tailor their offering to meet consumer needs.

5.1.1.2. Customer Personas

Creating a customer persona can be very beneficial for a business as it provides a clear and detailed understanding of the target audience. By crafting a representative profile of an ideal customer, businesses gain insights into the customers' needs, preferences, and pain points. This aids in tailoring products, services, and marketing strategies to effectively resonate with the intended market, resulting in more meaningful and targeted communication. Customer personas also guide product development by highlighting features that align with the identified persona's priorities. Furthermore, understanding the demographic and psychographic aspects of the audience allows businesses to make informed decisions on branding,

messaging, and positioning. Ultimately, the creation of customer personas fosters a customer-centric approach, enhancing customer satisfaction, loyalty, and driving overall business success.

In this part, based on market research, 11 hypothetical personas were created, 3 of them are presented here and the rest of them can be found on Annex II. All partners were asked to voluntarily help in the creation of the personas. Their purpose is to provide a clearer image of the target audience and guide both results development and potential future marketing efforts.

<i>Source</i>	<i>Specified benefits</i>
Cooper (1999)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase focus on the users and their goals - Facilitate effective communication about users
Cooper and Reimann (2002)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce necessary changes at the end of the development process - Build consensus and commitment to design - Help to measure a design's effectiveness - Define the product's feature set
Grudin and Pruitt (2002)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate effective communication within the project team - Help other related efforts such as marketing plans - Facilitate a focus on users and work contexts - Allow for extrapolation from partial knowledge of users to diverse contexts - Make assumptions about users explicit - Facilitate effective communication about the users
Long (2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase focus on a specific audience - Strengthen focus on the users during the development process - Lead to more user-friendly designs - Make the user needs more explicit - Guide decision making
Ma and LeRouge (2007)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate effective communication about the users - Enhance identification with the target users - Increase focus on user needs
Pruitt and Adlin (2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make assumptions about users explicit - Narrow the users being designed for - Lead to better design decisions - Increase engagement among the design team - Build empathy for the users

Figure 17: Benefits of persona use suggested in literature
(Source: Miaskiewicz and Kozar, 2011)

Persona #1 Nathalie B. Bold	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Liaison Officer at a National Biodiversity Bank ● Stakeholder category: Intermediary between NbS providers and financial world
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>There will likely be intermediaries between NbS providers and financiers at a national level (independent or appointed by a national government), who take it upon themselves to bundle and facilitate the transactions. One such is the (very recently established) Dutch National Biodiversity Bank Foundation (NBB), which <i>‘unburdens you when investing in biodiversity - transparent and guaranteed’</i>.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Nathalie B. Bold works as a Liaison Officer at the NBB. She has a background in accountancy and in her free time is an avid gardener, but she has little formal ecological knowledge. She acts as intermediary between landowners who want to enhance biodiversity on their property and with companies willing to finance it, whether or not to compensate for unavoidable loss of biodiversity due to their own activities. NBB is making efforts to develop the market for biodiversity credits. They published their principles, procedures and protocols in the first version of their online Handbook (2024, in Dutch); which could be revised in the future. They ask a landowner or municipality to make a plan outlining what needs to be done to achieve the biodiversity goals and what biodiversity gain can be achieved; after a quality check an agreement is drafted. Their Handbook describes in detail the procedures that apply.</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>NBB sees several challenges for the near future: first, they seek ways to further standardize the plan making phase; second, criteria and indicators that have to be met by a project need to be further defined; and third, they hope to streamline the monitoring costs, in order to work as efficiently as possible and reduce the overhead costs. They are accountable to the national government, so it is essential that they safeguard positive biodiversity outcomes for the projects in which they invest. They would be interested to explore innovative ways of investment, but do not have the knowledge or capabilities to do so themselves.</p>	
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <p>The description of the current situation is from NBB’s website; the Challenge however is based on personal assumptions and a previous publication (Gorissen et al. 2020), and needs to be verified.</p>	

Persona #2 Robert Doherty	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Senior executive at a financial institution ● Stakeholder category: Senior executive tasked with product design in a financial Institution, specifically a general (non-life) insurance company that sells insurance products to private individuals and corporations.
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Insurers play an important role in moderating the behaviour of companies and individuals. The design of insurance products influences; where people live (e.g. availability of flood cover can influence where people live), the types of products that companies produce (e.g. product liability may not be available for products under certain conditions), the products that people decide to buy (e.g. cost of car insurance) etc. An insurer's business model can vary depending on where they expect profitable opportunities, whether they can establish a market share or gain clients in other domains (e.g. sell car insurance so that they can also sell home insurance). While they may face long term exposures to risks relating to climate change and biodiversity loss, the business model in general insurance relies on relatively short-term products (12 months). Insurers can play a potential role in acknowledging the changing activities of EU landowners, from producers of food to potential producers of both food and ecosystem services.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Robert is tasked with introducing new products for the agri-food sector. This includes farm insurance (for individual farmers) as well as conventional commercial insurance covers for food processing companies (product liability, pollution covers etc.). The company wants to continue to deliver profitable product lines while increasing market share. Each division has been asked by the board to address issues around sustainability. Robert and his team have been asked to provide some guidance on how they can contribute to specific issues in relation to the agri-food sector, such as GHG emissions and biodiversity loss.</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Robert is aware of some nature-based solutions that have been implemented by farmers but does not yet know how this can be integrated into product design (either amending existing farm insurance products or designing new product formats).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How can he 'nudge' farmers to participate in NbS using insurance product design? 2. Does he need to consider a 'new' product type that supports the insurance needs of farmers that are producing both food and ecosystem services? <p>Within the two opportunities outlined above, how might these efforts affect their competitive position in the insurance market? How might it contribute to increasing the delivery of ES (relative to some baseline) and how could this be accounted/reported by Robert's company.</p>	
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What specific data might be required by Robert and his team to undertake option 1 above? ● To what extent would this activity (particularly Option 2) present risks for Robert in his career progression? ● For Option 1, what degree of confidence would Robert need to have about farmers' contribution to ES via NbS or would it be sufficient to know that the farmers are participants in an NbS? ● For Option 2, what specific covers might be required for a new product e.g. expanded compensation in relation to flood risk (e.g. slowing a river) or protection against costs of removing invasive species or disease/wildfire effects on native afforestation? ● What technologies are used by Robert to better understand, price and monitor these risks? 	

Persona #3 Alex Green	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Sustainability Manager at NutriGlobal Foods ● Stakeholder category: Agri-food sector / Non-Financial Company
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>As senior sustainability manager Alex is responsible for developing and implementing sustainability strategies to minimize the company's environmental impact, achieve its neutrality targets and reduce its carbon footprint.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Master's degree in Environmental Science and Business Administration. ● 10 years of experience in sustainability roles within the food and beverage industry, with a focus on sustainable sourcing, supply chain management, and corporate social responsibility (CSR). 	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>NutriGlobal Foods is a large, multinational corporation with a presence in over 50 countries. Established 50 years ago, it has built a strong reputation and market presence through its diverse range of popular packaged food and beverage products. Recently, the company has committed to achieving carbon neutrality by 2035 in response to growing environmental concerns and increasing pressure from consumers, investors, and regulatory bodies.</p> <p>NutriGlobal Foods sources its ingredients from a vast network of farmers and global suppliers. While cost and availability have historically driven sourcing decisions, there is now a push towards integrating more sustainable practices. Currently, only a fraction of ingredients are sustainably sourced.</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <p><i>"Finding the right balance between cost and sustainability is our biggest challenge."</i></p> <p>Alex needs data to build new business models (which may include NBS, Carbon Offset Investments, incentives for regenerative agriculture practices...) and evaluate products profitability if ingredients are sourced more sustainably.</p> <p>Alex wants to know which NBS may be relevant (=have significant impact) for NutriGlobal Foods.</p> <p>Decision-making factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cost-benefit analysis of sustainable versus conventional sourcing. ● Potential for long-term savings and risk mitigation. ● Impact on brand reputation and customer loyalty. ● Alignment with corporate sustainability goals and regulatory requirements. 	
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulty in quantifying the financial return on investment (ROI) for sustainable practices. ● Complexity in assessing and verifying the sustainability claims of suppliers. ● Are consumers willing to pay more for "eco-friendly" products? ● Who are the decision makers in the company? (Purchase? Supply-chain managers? Senior management?). 	

5.2. Next steps on Sustainability Plan

Having presented the basic methodology that will be used in developing the sustainability plan for project results together with the first elements of marketing strategy, the next step is to develop them as the project progresses. As project results take shape, exploitation pathways and opportunities will become clearer and together with the relevant partners the sustainability plan will start taking shape. In the next iteration of the deliverable (D7.6, M24) a preliminary of the sustainability plan can be presented alongside a more complete marketing strategy, including the Marketing Mix and specific Marketing KPIs that can be used for evaluation of future marketing activities, if results are deemed to be commercially exploitable.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable constitutes the first version of the “Integrated toolset for multiplying impact” (D7.5, M12). In this deliverable, three main aspects of the project were elaborated in order to ensure BIOFIN-EUs available resources towards successful impact maximisation.

First, a sound IPR management scheme that includes 2 workshops was presented, in order to identify all relevant IP (background knowledge) and clarify ownership (single or joint), screening and managing any new IP (foreground knowledge) that arises was presented, analysing the concrete steps that partners will follow for the purpose of examining the protection of any results that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited.

Next, the methodological framework for the development of a go-to-market strategy plan was developed including market analysis plan, market size estimations, analysis of the regulatory environment in the EU, external environment analysis through the use of PESTLE, internal analysis through the use of SWOT and a business model development literature review for helping in the selection of the correct tool for BM development. During the first year of the project a preliminary market analysis for the main relevant markets was presented and the analysis of the regulatory environment in the EU was conducted.

Finally, the first steps of a sustainability plan were written down, that at this stage contain the marketing plan for the potentially commercial results of the project and the main steps for the sustainability of the non-commercial results. Specific financial projections have yet to be explored since it is still very early, and they will be presented in a future iteration of the deliverable.

This deliverable is the first iteration and will be updated in M24. The final version will be delivered In M36.

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Annex I

“KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-4) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>		<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)</i>	<i>Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant</i>	<i>Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant</i>		
		<i>If “other”, please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>			<i>If “other”, please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>Other</i>
1	BIOFIN Database	Scientific		Research Organisations, Financial Actors	Research, teaching and open source for use by third parties.	Other		Open Data (where appropriate)
2	BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder	Scientific		NBS Provider, Researchers,	Research, teaching and open source for use by third parties.			
3	BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine	Scientific		Research Organisations, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy Makers & Standardisation bodies	Research, teaching and open source for use by third parties.			
4	Skills and Knowledge Accelerators	Training and education		Professional Ecosystem	Teaching, webinars			
5	BioFIN dashboard	Other	Scientific, NBSs, financiers, third parties	Providers, Professional Ecosystem, Policy				
6	Other individual or joint exploitable result (if any)							
Identified Background								
<i>Please validate the background described in the Consortium Agreement or revise accordingly</i>								
<p>This is the description in the Consortium Agreement for your organisation:</p> <p>As to MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY, it is agreed between the Parties that, to the best of their knowledge, Option 2: No data, know-how or information of MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY is Needed by another Party for implementation of the Project (Article 16.1 and its Annex 5 Grant Agreement, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights to background and results for implementing the action”) or Exploitation of that other Party’s Results (Article 16.1 and its Annex 5 Grant Agreement, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights for exploiting the results”).</p>								

Annex II

Personas #4 - #11

Persona #4 Frank and Daisy	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Dairy farmers ● Stakeholder category: Land stewards: Providers of NbS or nature positive land management.
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Throughout Europe, regular farming practices (and in particular animal farming) are a main cause for climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental damage. The context in which future changes have to take place is highly complex. Changes could vary from small (even cosmetic) adjustments, to far-reaching land use changes. Farmers are in the forefront of the climate and biodiversity crises, not only as causative agents but also because they are at risk of the consequences. At the same time, individual farmers are in a tight spot and have little room to maneuver. They show a wide variation in their willingness to change. I chose to describe a farmer couple for inclusiveness.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Dairy farmers Frank and Daisy, 35 and 37 years old, own a farm of intermediate size (100 cows, 20 sheep) in the Netherlands. They are strongly attached to their farm: Daisy inherited it from her father and in time they hope to pass it on to their daughter. The farm borders a forested nature reserve; they have good contacts with the NGO owners and even manage a pasture inside the reserve. Over the past years they've had difficulty making a living: prices for dairy were low and alternate water shortages and waterlogging of their fields made crop yields unpredictable. They lost some stock due to an outbreak of Q-fever, and barely escaped an outbreak of mad cow disease (BSE). It is likely that in the near future they will have to structurally reduce their stock to meet the European nitrogen regulations, but the regulatory outlook is unclear - as it has been over the past decades. The water and soil on their farm are in a bad state due to fertilizer pollution and intensive management practices, as are the diversity of plants, insects, birds, and soil organisms. All these would take years to recover. Frank and Daisy have considerable business debts. A substantial part of their annual income comes from CAP subsidies and National subsidies for nature positive interventions (that are only mildly successful).</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Frank and Daisy are considering changing their business model, but they are not sure what is logistically and financially possible. They will need loans or subsidies for new investments and to bridge the transition gap. They are frontrunners and are open to innovative scenarios, from organic dairy farming, organic or even regenerative crop farming, reforestation, or agroforestry. Diversifying in a combination of options is also considered. However, the bad state of the soil may make some of these options impossible. Each of the options will require substantial investments and leave them with significant stranded assets. In some cases the land may be devalued (e.g. (agro)forestry). Once the decision is made it will be irreversible because implementation takes several years and regulations will prevent another change. They realize that they should try working together with neighbouring farmers and the nature estate, for example for integral water management, and that some neighbours may be hostile to change. They also realize that they are not up to date with all the existing regulations and possibilities (such as which payments for Ecosystem Services they could consider, and how to go about this). So... how do they make a choice, how do they secure finance, and how do they manage the implementation?</p>	

Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona
NA

Persona #5 Silvio Tonalli

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Junior analyst ● Stakeholder category: Junior analyst on green and social impact bonds at a leading asset manager.
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Context/Rationale
Impact investors can be key stakeholders in bringing capital to fund nature-positive projects. Additionally, the persona is based on a real encounter at the sports club (Silvio has a good left hook).

Description of their current situation
After studying economics in Italy, Silvio earned a master's degree in financial economics at a reknown Dutch university. During his studies, he had the opportunity to complete multiple internships. It was during one of these that he discovered impact investing. He really enjoyed the concept of considering environmental and social outcomes, not just financial returns, when making investment decisions. As a result, he decided to specialize in this field. He recently joined a world leading asset manager operating in the Netherlands, where he works on the valuation of green and social impact bonds.

Their challenge
While Silvio is seeking impact, he understands the limited substitutability between capital returns and positive impacts. He is trying to delineate a feasible investment universe that satisfies its internal rate of return while also delivering positive social and environmental outcomes. Silvio is particularly interested in investment opportunities that help conserve or restore nature. He is conducting an initial assessment to better understand how nature-positive projects can be monetized.
In addition to capital returns, his investments need to meet a couple of other criteria. First, he is concerned that in some cases, nature conservation could have negative spillovers on social outcomes. He prefers to exclude such projects from his investment universe. Ideally, he would consider only investment opportunities that deliver co-benefits for both nature and people. Second, he would also prefer to exclude funding projects for which the nature-positive outcome seems too low or too uncertain. Indeed, it would be extremely disappointing to spend time and resources on projects that ultimately won't make a difference. Furthermore, the impact investing department in which he works is new, and picking the wrong projects in terms of impacts could jeopardize its future. Keeping all of this in mind, he googled a few words on nature-positive investments and ended up on the BIOFIN-EU dashboard.

Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona

- How does Silvio integrate impact into bond valuation?
- Which metrics does Silvio use to assess impact?

Persona #6 Leonhard "Leo" S.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: High-profile investor ● Stakeholder category: Advocate for Nature-Based Solutions (NbS)
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<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Leonhard, a renowned European actor from Switzerland, is diversifying his investment portfolio to include sustainable and environmentally friendly ventures. He recognizes the dual benefits of these investments: contributing positively to the environment and enhancing his public image. His involvement in NbS aligns with a growing trend among celebrities to champion environmental causes, providing visibility and credibility to these initiatives.</p>
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>With a career spanning over two decades, Leo has earned a reputation for his versatile acting skills and charismatic presence on screen. Off-screen, he is equally known for his shrewd financial acumen, consistently making profitable investments that have significantly increased his wealth. Recently, Leo has shifted his focus towards sustainable investments, particularly in the realm of Nature-Based Solutions. He actively participates in environmental summits and collaborates with organizations like the Dutch National Biodiversity Bank (NBB) to promote biodiversity initiatives. Despite his limited ecological knowledge, Leo leverages his financial expertise and public influence to support and advocate for NbS projects, aiming to create a positive impact on the environment and his brand.</p>
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Leo faces several challenges. Firstly, he must bridge the gap between his financial knowledge and the technical details of ecological projects. This requires a steep learning curve and reliance on experts. Secondly, Leo needs to ensure that his investments not only generate financial returns but also produce measurable positive impacts on biodiversity. This involves working closely with organizations like the NBB and utilizing platforms like BIOFIN-EU to standardize and streamline project planning, monitoring, and reporting processes. Lastly, as a public figure, Leo must balance his genuine concern for the environment with the perception of his motives, ensuring that his advocacy is seen as authentic rather than a mere publicity stunt.</p>
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <p>There are uncertainties regarding Leo’s depth of understanding and long-term dedication to these projects. How much ecological knowledge does he possess, and to what extent can he rely on BIOFIN-EU for support in deciding which NbS to invest in?</p> <p>Finally, will he maintain his commitment to sustainability if initial projects do not meet financial or the expected improvement on his public image?</p>

Persona #7 Simon Gray	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Peatlands Restoration Officer, Ulster Wildlife ● Stakeholder category: Conservation charity; non-governmental organisation (NGO)
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Conservation charities and NGOs have very limited financial resources, often relying on memberships and philanthropy to support the purchase and protection of land that harbors notable habitats or biodiversity. They face challenges in sourcing funds for beneficial land management and capturing and reporting outcomes in a comprehensive and compelling manner.</p>	

<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Ulster Wildlife, previously a member of The Wildlife Trust, is a conservation charity NGO dedicated to protecting and restoring nature on land and at sea. Their mission is to contribute to ending the climate and ecological emergencies by creating a society where nature is valued and integrated into daily life. The organization owns and manages 18 nature reserves throughout Northern Ireland, many of which are designated as Areas of Special Scientific Interest (ASSIs).</p> <p>Simon Gray, 42 years old, has worked with Ulster Wildlife for over a decade and has a deep personal commitment to peatland restoration. He holds a degree in Environmental Science and has extensive experience in habitat management and ecological restoration. Simon is responsible for overseeing the implementation of the peatland restoration strategy aimed at rewetting and ecologically restoring degraded lowland raised bogs and upland blanket bogs. His goal is to reverse carbon loss and recreate carbon sinks while enhancing peatland biodiversity and connecting sites into a recovery network.</p>
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Simon is faced with securing adequate funding to undertake major restoration works across multiple sites and implementing a comprehensive outreach program to educate the public and stakeholders about the importance of peatland restoration. Although EU funding, such as PEACEPLUS, is available, Simon believes that additional funds might be sourced from private entities interested in carbon offsetting and biodiversity credits.</p>
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <p>Simon requires support to quantify, capture, and report on carbon fluxes and biodiversity-related management activities. This data is crucial for reporting to Ulster Wildlife members, funding bodies, and private companies that invest in peatland restoration. He faces difficulties in finding and using the right tools and methodologies to measure and communicate these outcomes effectively.</p>

Persona #8 James Smith	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: A Fellow of the Institute of Chartered Engineers and Senior Partner in the medium sized family firm of Consulting Engineers, Smith and Nephew. The company has offices in several Irish towns and cities and operates throughout the UK and in EU countries. ● Stakeholder category: The firm has advised in recent decades on major schemes on infrastructure for flood control and urban drainage which has become an important focus and profit centre for the company.
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>As senior partner James is responsible for the strategic future development of Smith and Nephew and for the recruitment and development of senior staff in current and new business areas.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Up until now Smith and Nephew have concentrated their expertise on grey infrastructure solutions involving construction of concrete pipeline, drains and river course realignment and canalisation. Smith and Nephew are concerned that such solutions although effective in their primary purpose are carbon intensive, contribute to further climate change and have a negative impact on biodiversity both in the water and throughout the land area of the river catchment.</p>	

<p>Their challenge</p> <p>During the last decade, James, with more forward-looking partners in Smith and Nephew, and trainee and junior staff have attended a number of Workshops on Nature Based Solutions at the ICE Head Quarters in London and in EU centres. The huge challenge James must face is whether Smith and Nephew should appoint a senior member of staff at partner level to take the firm forward as specialist advisors on Green Infrastructure in flood control and urban drainage both as alternative and complementary solutions to their traditional focus on hard engineering solutions.</p>
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <p>James is concerned that embracing alternative green solution may be premature, he is also concerned that Smith and Nephew maintain their position as specialists in flood control and urban drainage in competition with multinational companies such as AECOM and RPS who are already investing in this area. Key questions in his mind are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can NBSs address large scale projects in isolation or when combined with traditional engineering solutions? ● Can NBSs be demonstrated as cost effective against traditional solutions? ● Municipalities throughout the EU can easily raise tens of millions of euros on the municipal bond markets for hard engineering, but will the finance sector be equally convinced by NBSs ● Will Green Infrastructure prove more or less durable than Grey Infrastructure and will it have higher or lower maintenance costs? ● James knows that NBSs provide a range of nature co-benefits in addition to flood control and drainage services. He wonders how municipalities investing in NBSs can maximise the benefits of these and whether Smith and Nephew would need to employ an ecologist to advise clients on how to maximise these perhaps in partnership with a Wildlife Trust.

Persona #9 Dr. Sophia Patel	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Senior marine biologist ● Stakeholder category: NBS Provider for Coral Reef Conservation
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Dr. Sophia Patel is a senior marine biologist working for a company called Ocean Solutions. She is responsible for managing and maintaining a nature-based solution project that aims to restore a local coral reef and improve marine biodiversity. The coral reef conservation is of high importance because it maintains the health and resilience of the coral reef ecosystem and contributes to the well-being of the local community by providing jobs, increasing tourism and improve fisheries management.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Dr. Patel has extensive experience in managing and analysing large datasets related to marine ecosystems. She needs a robust and tailored platform that can help her effectively manage the project's data and reporting requirements, ensure compliance with regulatory frameworks, and balance the environmental and financial goals of the NBS project ensuring that it is both ecologically effective and financially viable.</p>	

<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Dr. Patel faces the challenge of managing the complexity and volume of data related to the NBS project, ensuring data quality and consistency, and integrating data from various sources. She also needs to collaborate with stakeholders to ensure the project's social and environmental sustainability. The project may face funding challenges, which can limit the scope and scale of the interventions and make it harder to achieve the desired outcomes.</p>
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How can Dr. Patel ensure the long-term success and sustainability of her NBS project? ● What are the most effective ways for her to stay informed with the latest research and methodologies in marine biology coupled with funding sources and financial instruments? ● How can she balance the environmental and financial goals of her NBS project with protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems?

Persona #10 Dr. Maria Rodriguez	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Occupation: Senior policy advisor at a Ministry of Environment ● Stakeholder category: Policy Maker
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Dr. Maria Rodriguez is a senior policy advisor at the Ministry of Environment, responsible for developing and implementing policies related to environmental conservation, NBS and sustainable development. Policy makers are in the forefront of the environmental protection, sustainable and economic development of an area. Effective environmental policies can contribute to climate change mitigation, biodiversity loss and pollution while sustainable and economic development policies balance economic growth, social equity, create jobs, stimulate innovation, and reduce costs associated with environmental degradation.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>Dr. Rodriguez has over 20 years of experience in policy development and implementation. She needs a robust and tailored platform that can help her effectively manage and analyse large datasets related to biodiversity, ecosystem services and financing opportunities and provide data-driven insights to support policy decisions.</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <p>Dr. Rodriguez faces the challenge of staying informed about the latest research and methodologies in ecology, Nature Base Solutions and ensuring that policy decisions are based on the best available evidence. She also needs to collaborate with stakeholders to ensure that policies are effective and sustainable. This requires her to manage and analyse large datasets effectively, ensuring that data-driven insights support policy decisions.</p>	
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How can Dr. Rodriguez ensure that policy decisions are based on the best available evidence? ● What are the most effective ways for her to collaborate with stakeholders to ensure that policies are effective and sustainable? ● How can she stay up-to-date with the latest research and methodologies in protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems? ● How can Dr. Rodriguez balance environmental and financial goals, ensuring that policies promote sustainable development, NBS and reduce environmental degradation? 	

Persona #11 The Municipality of Malmö in Sweden	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stakeholder category: A municipality (politicians/administrators)
<p>Context/Rationale</p> <p>Several hundred years ago, Södra Varvsviken in Malmö, a coastal area in the Southern part of Sweden, was a shallow bay with eelgrass, red algae, bluefish, and lots of fish. The depth was only a few meters, so the sun reached the bottom of the sea, and the bay was a nursery for various fish species. The harbor area has since been exploited by industrial activity and the sediments in the seabed became heavily polluted. They also needed to deepen the seabed for boats making the place too deep and dark for eelgrass to grow. Today there is no life left on the seabed. The seabed is as big as seven football pitches and is located within a very new residential area in Malmö.</p> <p>The goal of the project started by Malmö municipality is to increase the biodiversity so that many of the disappeared species would return. Especially important for biodiversity is eelgrass, which is the sea's nursery for small fish.</p>	
<p>Description of their current situation</p> <p>A project that aims to restore a healthy marine environment that once existed. The contaminated sediments have been covered by crushed stone and sand, which encapsulated the industry toxins in the seabed. The depth of the harbor is reduced to a maximum of four meters so that the sunlight reaches down. The shallower water also makes the harbor safer for residential housing. The Malmö harbor is an experimental project, and the municipality has plans for restoring several other areas in the harbor area nearby. The harbor area is also part of a residential development.</p>	
<p>Their challenge</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. They have an interest in exploring re-wilding by letting the environmental improvements happen in a natural way without any human involvement (after the sand-capping and reduced water depth). This is cheaper than active restoration, but more uncertain and it takes time. They need to collaborate with researchers, but they also need more information about re-wilding. 2. Although rewilding is cheaper, funds are needed. In particular, if this is to be scaled up. Right now, the municipality plans to fund this through taxes. But they are interested in other financial solutions, including money from sales of land/residential development around the area. They are interested in knowing more about different financial solutions. 3. Some people involved are rather knowledgeable but would like to know more about what is happening at both the national and EU-level when it comes to biodiversity policies. 	
<p>Unknowns and uncertainties about the Persona</p> <p>There are some uncertainties about the time it will take for the seabed to recover and whether it would be successful in the first place. Another option is to intentionally plant eelgrass beds. This is more expensive, but also faster. If so, they will need financial resources not only for sand-capping seabeds but also for planting eelgrass.</p>	